

PHYTOREMEDIATION POTENTIALS OF PENNISETUM PURPUREUM AND *Leuceana Leucocephala* AMENDED WITH ORGANO-MINERAL FERTILIZER AND BRASSINOLIDE FOR SELECTED HEAVY METALS REMOVAL FROM CRUDE OIL CONTAMINATED SOIL

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ABSTRACT

Soil and water pollution due to oil exploration activities has become a key environmental challenge in Nigeria's Niger Delta region. Phytoremediation is an environmentally friendly approach in managing soil pollution. This study aimed to evaluate the potential of some native plant species for phytoremediation of heavy metals in crude oil-polluted soils. Two native plant species (*Pennisetum purpureum* and *Leuceana leucocephala*) were studied under field condition with four levels of crude oil pollution (0, 2.5, 5.0 and 7.5 % (w/w), organo-mineral fertilizer (5 t/ha) and Brassinolide (250 ml per plant) using a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. Results obtained showed that there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the absorption of heavy metals by the plants after 6 months of pollution. The plants partitioned more heavy metals (Pb, Ni, Cd) to the roots and stem than the leaf. *Pennisetum purpureum* had the highest absorption efficiency of 79.8 %, followed by *Leuceana leucocephala* (61.0 %), against (41.0 %) in non-amended soils and (38.6 %) in non-vegetated soil. The possible reasons for the high uptake of heavy metals by these two plants were due to such mechanisms as phytoextraction (metal accumulation in plants), application of organomineral fertilizer and brassinolide increased metal mobility in the soil, thus facilitating the remediation by both plants. Therefore, *P. purpureum* and *L. leucocephala* have good potential to bioaccumulate heavy metals from crude oil-polluted soils and are recommended.

Key words: Crude Oil, Heavy metals, *Pennisetum purpureum*, *Leuceana leucocephala*

INTRODUCTION Atomic weight and atomic numbers. The Contamination of soil with petroleum common heavy metals/ metalloids include: hydrocarbons has become a global phenomenon. With the development of arsenic (As), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), nickel industrialisation and urbanisation, the (Ni) and chromium (Cr). Although some are abundance of heavy metals in the essential, such as Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Zn and are environment has increased enormously required for physiological and biochemical during the past decades, raising significant processes during the plant life cycle concerns throughout the world (Suman *et al.* (Cempel and Nickel, 2006); however, they *al.*, 2018; Ashraf *et al.*, 2019). Heavy metals may become toxic when present in higher concentrations are a group of metallic chemical elements. Although heavy metals are naturally elements that have relatively high densities, occurring in the soil, geologic and

anthropogenic activities increase the concentration of them to amounts that may be harmful for both plants and animal due to their potentials toxicity which affect their physiology and development (Ijah et al., 2019). Therefore, remediation of soil contaminated with heavy metals is of paramount importance. Phytoremediation that uses the remarkable ability of plants to concentrate elements and compounds from the environment and to metabolise various molecules in their tissues appears very promising for the removal of pollutants from the environment (Gurbisu and Alkorta, 2003). Several reports (Cho-Ruk et al., 2006; Olivares et al., 2013; Olantunji et al., 2014 and Ng et al., 2016) indicated that some plants such as *Pennisetum purpureum*, *Panicum maximum*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Vertiver grass*, Castor beans etc. have shown the ability to absorb and hyper-accumulate metals contaminant such as lead, cadmium, arsenic and various radionuclides from soil. Therefore the objective of this study was to evaluate the potential of *Penisetum purpureum* and *Leuceana leucocephala* for phytoremediation of heavy metals from crude oil polluted soil amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and phytohormonal Treatment (Brassinolide).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The study was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Akwa Ibom State University, which lies between Latitude $4^{\circ}30'1$ and $533'N$ and Longitude $7^{\circ}25'8$ and $825'E$ with a mean annual rainfall of over 3000mm and annual temperature varies between 26 - 30C.

Experimental materials used/sources

The experimental materials used were crude oil, organo-mineral fertilizer and plant growth hormones (Brassinolide). Top soil was taken from the Teaching and

Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Akwa Ibom State University. *Pennisetum purpureum* and *Leuceana leucocephala* were transplanted within the experimental area.

Field Experiment

The experimental site was manually cleared, stumped, tilled and mound beds measuring 1 m x 1 m made. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 15 treatments replicated thrice. Each block was separated from each other with an alley of 1m and each plot by 0.5 m. Crude oil was applied to specified plots by sprinkling from perforated cans. The aim was to simulate the condition of a major oil spill. The plots were left undisturbed for one week. After one week it was tilled and organo-mineral fertilizer applied to specified plots at the rate of 5 t/ha. Two weeks after application of the fertilizer, young seedlings measuring 5 cm of *Leuceana leucocephala* and *Pennisetum purpureum* were sown on the prepared beds to a depth of 5 cm. Twenty-eight (28) days after planting, plant growth hormones (Brassinolide) was diluted at the rate of 1 ml to 1000 ml (1litre) of distilled water and was foliarly applied to specified plots at the rate of 15 ml/plant. Soil samples were collected from each plot at 3 and 6 months after pollution for laboratory analysis.

The treatment for the field experiment were:

T₁ = 2.5 % crude oil polluted soil + organo-mineral fertilizer (OF), no planting or brassinolide

T₂ = 5.0 % crude oil polluted soil + OF, no planting or brassinolide

T₃ = 7.5 % crude oil polluted soil + OF, no planting or brassinolide

T₄ = 2.5 % crude oil polluted soil + no OF or brassinolide under *Pennisetum purpureum*

T₅ = 5.0 % crude oil polluted soil + no OF or brassinolide under *P. purpureum*

T₆ = 7.5 % crude oil polluted soil + no OF or brassinolide under *P. purpureum*

- T₇ = 2.5 % crude oil polluted soil + OF+ brassinolide under *P.purpureum*
- T₈ = 5.0 % crude oil polluted soil + OF + brassinolide under *P.purpureum*
- T₉ = 7.5 % crude oil polluted soil + OF + brassinolide under *P. purpureum*
- T₁₀ = 2.5 % crude oil polluted soil + no OF or brassinolide under *Leuceana leucocephala*
- T₁₁ = 5.0 % crude oil polluted soil + no OF or brassinolide under *L. leucocephala*
- T₁₂ = 7.5 % crude oil polluted soil + no OF or brassinolide under *L. leucocephala*
- T₁₃ = 2.5 % crude oil polluted soil + OF + brassinolide under *L. leucocephala*
- T₁₄ = 5.0 % crude oil polluted soil + OF + brassinolide under *L.leucocephala*
- T₁₅ = 7.5 % crude oil polluted soil+ OF + brassinolide under *L. leucocephala*

SOIL SAMPLING AND LABORATORY ANALYSIS

These soils samples collected after treatment application in the field were analyzed in the laboratory for heavy metals in soils and

plant tissue at the end of the experiment at six (6) months. The heavy metals analyzed were those that are known to accumulate in higher concentration in plants affected by petroleum hydrocarbon. The heavy metals are Cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni). Portions of the air-dried samples (10 g) of plants harvested from the experimental site were homogenized and digested in nitric acid before analyzing for lead, cadmium and nickel using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Properties of the crude oil and organo-mineral fertilizer used for the study

The details chemical properties of the crude oil and organo-mineral fertilizer used for the study are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Characteristics of crude oil used for the study

Parameter	Specific value
Specific gravity (g/cm ³)	0.834 0.28
Viscosity (CP)	85.5 12.61
Carbon (%)	1.48 0.47
Hydrogen (%)	0.50
Sulphur(%)	0.13 88.1
Nitrogen(%)	
Oxygen (%)	
Trace metals(%)	
Gas: oilratio	

Table 2: Chemical properties of organo-mineral fertilizer used for the field experiment

Properties	Value
N(%)	s 2.8
P(%)	1.2
K(%)	2.2
Moisture (%)	1.4
Total organic matter (%)	4.0

Heavy metal contents in soils Content of heavy metals [Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni) and Cadmium (Cd)] in soils at 3 months after crude oil pollution

The content of heavy metals Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni) and Cadmium (Cd) in soils under different treatments in the field at 3 month after crude oil pollution are presented in Table 3. The unplanted soil polluted with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer without brassinolide had a significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher content of Pb than other treatments. The lowest content of Pb was in planted soil polluted with 2.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide. Generally, the content of Pb across the treated soils significantly exceeded the permissible limit of 85 mg/kg in soils (WHO, 1996). The increase in Pb content may be due to the pollution of the soil with crude oil. Hinojosa *et al.*, (2004) reported an increase in Pb content as a result of crude oil pollution. The highest level of nickel content was in the unplanted soil polluted with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer, without brassinolide while the lowest was in soils polluted with 2.5 or 5.0 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and

brassinolide, under *P. purpureum* and *L. leucocephala* (Table 3) Vwioko *et al.*, (2006) and Hinojosa *et al.* (2004) also reported a high accumulation of nickel due to the presence of crude oil. The Ni content in the treated soils were higher than the permissible limit of 35 mg/kg (WHO, 1996). Cadmium (Cd) content in the soil was significantly higher in the unplanted soil polluted with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer without brassinolide than all treatments (Table 3). The lowest content of cadmium was in planted soils polluted with 2.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral and brassinolide. The cadmium content in all the soils exceeded the permissible limit of 0.8 mg/kg (WHO, 1996). The marked reduction in the content of heavy metals, especially in planted soils polluted with crude oil and amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide may be attributed to complexation with organic molecules from the fertilizer or the uptake of these metals by the plant.

TABLE 3: Content of heavy metals (Pb, Ni, Cd) in the soil at 3 months after crude oil pollution

Treatment	Lead (Pb)	Nickel (Ni) mg/kg	Cadmium
T1	253.33de	55.67ef	4.26c
T2	379.00b	62.67cd	5.01b
T3	500.67a	72.33a	5.33a
T4	220.00ef	51.33f	3.13f
T5	280.00cd	58.0de	3.80e
T6	294.33cd	65.33bc	3.98d
T7	126.67h	36.33h	2.13j
T8	148.00gh	40.67h	2.41i
T9	165.00gh	45.33g	2.61h
T10	227.00ef	53.67ef	3.23f
T11	291.67cd	62.33cd	3.99d
T12	317.33c	67.67b	4.36c
T13	135.00gh	38.00h	2.21j
T14	136.67gh	40.00h	2.550h
T15	183.33fg	46.67g	2.78g

Means in the same column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different at 5% probability level

Content of heavy metals [Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni) and Cadmium (Cd)] in soils at 6 months after crude oil pollution The content of heavy metals Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni) and Cadmium (Cd) in soils under different treatments in the field at 6 months after crude oil pollution are presented in Table 4. The unplanted soil polluted with 7.5 % crude oil, treated with organo-mineral fertilizer without brassinolide had the highest ($P < 0.05$) contents of lead among treatments while the lowest content of lead was in soil polluted with 2.5% crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide under *P. purpureum*. Generally, the content of lead in all the treated soils were above the permissible limits of 85mg/kg in unpolluted soils, WHO (1996).

The content of nickel exceeded the WHO (1996) permissible limits of 35mg/kg in all the treated soils (Table 4), except for soils treated with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer without plant and brassinolide, soils polluted with 5.0 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide under *P. purpureum* and soil polluted with 2.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide under *L. leucocephala*. Vwioko et al., (2006) and Hinojosa et al., (2014) reported high accumulation of nickel in soil due to the presence of crude oil. Cadmium concentration followed a similar trend as Ni (Table 4). Polluted soils with 2.5% crude, amended with organo-mineral fertilizers and brassinolide under *P. purpureum* had the lowest content of Cd.

The content of cadmium across soils, with crude oil and amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide may be attributed to complexation with organic molecules from the fertilizer or the uptake of these metals by the plant.

irrespective of the treatment, was higher than the permissible limit of 0.8 mg/kg in the soil (WHO, 1996). However, the significant reduction in the content of heavy metals especially in planted soils polluted

Table 4: Content of heavy metals Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni) and Cadmium (Cd) in the soil at 6 months after crudeoilpollution

Treatment	Lead (Pb) mg/kg	Nickel (Ni) mg/kg	Cadmium(Cd) mg/kg
T1	240.00d	45.67de	3.23c
T2			
T3	370.00b	56.67b	4.08b
T4	440.00a	63.00a	4.23a
T5			
T6	197.67e	41.33ef	2.84d
T7	244.67d	48.33cd	3.01cd
T8			
T9	273.33c	51.67bc	3.15cd
T10	108.00h	29.67h	1.17h
T11			
T12	124.67gh	34.33gh	1.31ef
T13	139.00fg	36.67fg	1.50g
T14			
T15	204.67e	43.67de	2.96d
	233.67d	48.67cd	3.29c
	258.67cd	53.33bc	3.23c
	119.67gh	33.33gh	1.25ef
	130.33fgh	37.33fg	1.49g
	154.33f	41.00ef	1.60e

Means in the same column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different at 5% probability level

Heavy metal concentrations in plants

The concentration of lead (Pb) in the root, stem and leaf of the two plant species across treatments is presented in Figure 1. *Pennisetum purpureum* raised in soils treated with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizers and brassinolide had the highest (P ≤ 0.05) concentration of Pb in the roots compared with other treatments. Generally, the roots of *P. purpureum* and *L. leucocephala* retained

the highest concentration of Pb with tissue abundance in the order root > stem > leaf. This shows that, the plants are hyper-extractors of lead (Pb) in crude oil polluted soil and can be used for phytoremediation. Olatunji et al., (2014) and Udom et al., (2012) reported that most plants ordinarily accumulate heavy metals mainly in the root and less in the leaves or in the edible parts.

Figure. 1 Concentration of Pb in the stem, root and leaf of *Pennisetum purpureum* and *Leuceana leucocephala* under different treatments in the field after 6 months after pollution

Concentration of Nickel in plant root, stem and leaf

The accumulation of nickel (Ni) in the vegetative organs of the plants differed significantly (Figure 2). *P. purpureum* grown on soil contaminated with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide significantly (P < 0.05) had the highest content of Ni in the roots. The lowest content of nickel in the root, stem and leaf was observed in soil polluted with 2.5% crude oil, without

organo-mineral fertilizer or brassinolide under *L. leucocephala*. Schnoor *et al.*, (1995) reported that plants grown in soil with high metal concentration were likely to have an elevated metal uptake and accumulation in tissues. The low accumulation of the trace elements in plants grown in unamended soils may be due to several factors such as the toxic effect of the crude oil, lack of nutrients and presence of competing ions (Prasad *et al.*, 1999).

Figure. 2. Concentration of nickel (Ni) in the stem, root and leaf of *Pennisetum purpureum* and *Leuceana leucocephala* in the field 6 months after pollution

Concentration of Cadmium in plant sink for Cd accumulation. Peer *et al.* (2005) reported that plants used for phytoremediation must have the ability to accumulate heavy metals and must be adaptable to the environment. Similarly, Abdel-Salem (2012) reported that *P. purpureum* is an efficient phytoremediator plants for Cd uptake. According to Ebbs and Kochin (1979), some plant species have the capacity to absorb and accumulate certain metals in their shoot and roots at levels that are toxic to ordinary plants.

P. purpureum planted in soil polluted with 7.5 % crude oil, amended with organo-mineral fertilizer and brassinolide had the highest content of Cd in the root. A similar trend was also observed for soils planted with *L. leucocephala*. The concentration of Cd in the two plants were in the order; root > stem > leaf. The high accumulation of Cd in the roots of both plants implies that Cd translocation from the soil to the root was substantially higher and the roots acted as a

Figure 3: Concentration of Cadmium (Cd) in the stem, root and leaf of *Pennisetum purpureum* and *Leuceanaleucocephala* in the field 6 months after pollution

CONCLUSION

Result from the field trials showed that there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the uptake of heavy metals in plant tissues of *P. purpureum* and *L. leucocephala*. The concentration of lead (Pb), nickel (Ni) and cadmium (Cd) in plant tissues were in the order: root > stem > leaf with the application of organo-mineral fertilizer and

brassinolide. Having ascertained the performance and efficacy for remediation of heavy metals in crude oil polluted soil, they are therefore recommended especially where cost effectiveness and eco-friendly methods are of paramount consideration. Further screening of more native plant species should be explored.

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